

MODERN TRENDS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DOMESTIC AND INTERNATIONAL TOURISM IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

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ABSTRACT

Today, the role of tourism in the world economy is strengthening, and it is rapidly developing as one of the important macroeconomic sectors. Within the framework of the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 26, 2023 "On Additional Measures for the Accelerated Development of the Tourist Potential of the Republic and Further Increase in the Number of Local and Foreign Tourists," the tourism potential of the Republic of Karakalpakstan has been improved.

Today, the role of tourism in the world economy is strengthening, and it is rapidly developing as one of the important macroeconomic sectors. Within the framework of the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 26, 2023 "On Additional Measures for the Accelerated Development of the Tourist Potential of the Republic and Further Increase in the Number of Local and Foreign Tourists," the tourism potential of the Republic of Karakalpakstan has been improved.

Development targets for 2022-2026 have been defined. Since 2016, the number of foreign tourists visiting Karakalpakstan has increased. The majority of tourists came from France, the USA, Italy, Russia, Germany, Korea, Great Britain, China, and Japan. [1]. To provide tourists with the highest possible quality services, new hotels, campsites, and guest houses have been organized. Also, in order to develop tourism infrastructure in Karakalpakstan, tourist accommodation facilities were launched and tour operator entities were created. Recently, many tourists visiting the republic have also increased attention to ecotourism. Taking into account the importance of various cultural and entertainment events in the development of domestic tourism in Uzbekistan, attracting tourists, taking into account the specifics of each region, various cultural and entertainment, sports, exhibitions, and other mass events were held in the city of Nukus, such as a drone show, the "Spring Tourist Season Has Begun: Welcome to Travel!," the "STIXIYA" electronic music festival, and the "Muynak Rally" car race. In 2019, in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 16, 2019, No. 37 "On Measures for the Comprehensive Socio-Economic Development of the Muynak District of the Republic of Karakalpakstan," the Alley of Craftsmen of the Muynak District, the Alley of Poets, and the Yurt Crafts Center were built and put into operation. An "Open Skies" regime has been introduced at Nukus International Airport, applying the "fifth freedom of the air." It should be noted that previously the airport did not have such capabilities. The Mizdakhon archaeological complex, located in the Khojeyli

district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is one of the complexes with prospects for the development of pilgrimage tourism. Among the monuments of Nazlumkhan Suluv, Rajab Khalifa, Shamun Nabi, Jomard Qassob, and Gaur Qala of the Mizdakhon archaeological complex, the Nazlumkhan Suluv monument occupies a special place. Alongside such masterpieces of architecture as Ismail Samaniy, Khoja Ahmed Yassawi, Muhammad Tekesh, Sanjar Turebek Khanum, Nazlumkhan Suluv stands as an invaluable monument of our people. Located on the territory of the Mizdakhkan Reserve Museum, this monument is known among the local population as "qiz uyi," "sufi qizining uyi" or "palace" with a total area of 30x30 meters [2]. In 2024, the number of tourists who visited our republic amounted to 2.2 million, of which 200 thousand were foreign tourists. Basically, by 2025, it is planned to increase the number of tourists visiting the republic to 3 million, including the number of foreign tourists to 400 thousand, the number of domestic tourists to 2.6 thousand, and the export of tourist services to 50 million dollars[3]. As a result of the special attention paid by our esteemed President to the sphere of tourism and culture, favorable conditions have been created, and the number of tourists visiting our country is increasing year by year. According to the global media portal "BBC Travel," Uzbekistan was included in the list of the 25 best destinations to travel in 2025. In addition, citizens of more than 90 countries, including Great Britain, Canada, and Australia, can come to Uzbekistan visa-free, which significantly simplifies travel and opens up new opportunities for tourists. [4]. It should also be noted that February 25th has become a tradition in the Republic of Karakalpakstan to be widely celebrated as "Jüöyeri gyrtik kúni," and various events are planned this year as well. On February 25, at the ethno-tourist center "Karakalpak village" in the city of Nukus, "Júweri gúrtik kúni" was widely celebrated as a holiday. This holiday is widely celebrated not only in the city of Nukus, but also throughout the republic. In order to develop tourism in the Ustyurt Plain in the Kungrad district, it is planned to organize "Desert" and "Pilgrimage" tourism at major pilgrimage sites in the district, such as "Ustyurt Plain," "Dovud Ota," "Bugrakhon Ota," and "Payg'ambar qizi." In the development of tourism in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, mainly domestic, that is, national, regional, and local tourism is of great importance. Supporting the arrival of tourists from neighboring regions and districts is also one of the important tasks. Creating conditions for them is one of the main issues. It is necessary to take marketing measures and place Karakalpakstan's tourism products on international tourism platforms. In conclusion, special attention was paid to the development of tourism in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Because the region had all the possibilities for the development of the industry. Nevertheless, in the first years of independence, this was achieved only through the activities of museums. Because for the system to develop in modern ways, it was necessary to attract large material resources. In the period after 2016, with increased state attention and support to the sphere, opportunities were created for the development of all spheres of tourism. Based on the foregoing, there is a need to develop and improve tourism in the regions. Therefore, it should be noted that the Republic of Karakalpakstan should have its place in the tourism market and, taking into account its importance in the economy, regardless of the form of ownership of the development of the regional tourism market, it should be carried out primarily on the basis of direct assistance and support from the state. Currently, the development of organizational and

economic mechanisms for attracting investments in the tourism sector, which is part of the service sector, is of great importance.

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